

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

TEMPERATURE TOLERANCE

Yield of rice under chronic air pollution stress, as influenced by soil nitrogen

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We evaluated the response of varieties Co 43, GR3, and TKM9 to chronic air pollution by a fertilizer plant (GSFC in Baroda, India) during 1985 wet season. Seeds were exposed 350 m in the windward direction from the pollution source. Air pollutant daily averages at the test site were 16.5 $\mu\text{g SO}_2/\text{m}^3$, 25 $\mu\text{g NO}_x/\text{m}^3$, 16.4 mg NH_3/m^3 , 0.403 $\mu\text{M F}/\text{cm}^2$, and 233.7 μg suspended particulate matter/ m^3 .

Table 1. Effect of air pollution on the yield attributes of rice cultivars.^a Baroda, India.

Cultivar	Regime	Panicle length (cm)		Panicles/plant		Spikelets/panicle		Filled grains/plant		Unfilled grains/plant	
		C	P	C	P	C	P	C	P	C	P
Co 43	LN	16.5	10.5	2.6	3.8	7.3	4.8	131.0	1.4	61.0	180.8
	HN	15.2	14.4	3.0	4.0	6.3	6.1	127.0	17.6	68.6	191.8
GR3	LN	18.8	14.0	2.8	11.2	8.6	6.9	116.2	156.2	45.0	264
	HN	15.8	14.4	4.2	11.6	7.9	6.9	50.0	246.2	95.8	271
TKM9	LN	16.6	13.9	3.4	6.0	5.3	5.2	102.8	125.2	43.0	156.8
	HN	14.7	11.8	3.8	5.0	5.0	4.3	52.8	47.2	50.0	107.8
Mean		16.3	13.2	3.3	6.9	6.7	5.7	96.6	88.0	60.6	195.4
CD (0.05)		2.60		3.90		2.73		3.70		2.50	

^aC = control, P = polluted, LN = low nitrogen, HN = high nitrogen.

At 30 d after seeding, seedlings potted in 8 kg soil were fertilized with N as urea (low level, 0.069 g N/pot 2 times; high, 1.69 g N/pot 3 times). Controls

were maintained 10 km away from the test site, using the same soil and water: GR3 performed better under high N and TKM9 under low N (Table 1,2). □

Table 2. Effect of air pollution on yield of rice cultivars. Baroda, India.

Cultivar	Regime	Dry wt (g) of filled grains/plant		Dry wt (g) of unfilled grains/plant		Straw wt (g/plant)		100-grain wt (g)		Yield (g)		Harvest index	
		C	P	C	P	C	P	C	P	C	P	C	P
Co 43	LN	1.81	0.02	0.15	0.35	3.19	7.97	3.19	1.20	5.19	8.34	0.361	0.002
	HN	1.63	0.19	0.12	0.42	3.36	5.56	3.36	1.10	6.74	6.17	0.309	0.031
GR3	LN	1.90	2.32	0.20	1.21	3.02	5.38	3.02	5.38	5.12	8.81	0.365	0.256
	HN	0.74	3.75	0.43	1.31	2.71	5.55	2.71	5.55	3.89	10.05	0.184	0.377
TKM9	LN	1.66	2.10	0.15	0.65	2.84	3.67	2.84	3.66	4.65	6.42	0.363	0.293
	HN	0.84	0.75	0.21	0.36	2.63	3.02	2.63	3.02	3.68	4.13	0.231	0.180
Mean		1.43	1.52	0.21	0.72	2.96	5.19	2.87	3.32	4.88	7.32	0.302	0.190
CD (0.05)		0.59		0.29		1.29		0.07		1.86		0.005	

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HYBRID RICE

Identification and classification of fertility restorers and maintainers for cytoplasmic male sterile line V20A

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Since rice is a strictly self-pollinated crop, heterosis breeding must have an effective male sterility and restorer system to produce a bulk quantity of hybrid seeds. Among the commercially usable cytoplasmic male sterile lines, V20A is one of the most stable.

V20A was crossed with 40 indica varieties to identify their fertility-

restoring ability and the maintenance capacity of V20A. The F_1 s were raised in 4 replications, each consisting of 40 plots with an interplot spacing of 50 cm. Each plot had 1 row of 5 single-plant hills, with a spacing of 25 cm between hills. At maturity, all plants were harvested, and their grain fertility calculated. The varieties were then